

Meijer, Eva. *Multispecies Dialogues: Doing Philosophy with Animals, Children, the Sea and Others*. Amsterdam University Press, 2025.

Rooted interdisciplinarily across animal ethics, environmental thought, political philosophy, and more, *Multispecies Dialogues* continues Eva Meijer's engagement with non-human communication, voice, and interspecies democracy (e.g., Meijer 2013, 2019). Expanding on their previous works in these areas, this new book offers a fascinating glimpse into the everyday dimensions of multispecies coexistence, asking how we might do philosophy not *about* but *with* non-human others.

The book's guiding idea is that learning to live better with non-human others requires us to speak differently with them. Thinking meaningfully about multispecies coexistence, Meijer argues, also means including non-humans in the very process of creating the conditions of living together. They develop this idea by first broadening the notions of conversation and dialogue beyond verbal exchange, attending instead to other forms of communication already present in our shared lives with non-humans, such as touch, greetings, and movement.

Meijer's reflections are further guided by the aim of cultivating what they call "worldliness," a virtue that allows us to live more attentively and responsively with members of our own and other species.

Meijer conceives of their writing as a dialogue with the reader, whereby meaning emerges through shared interpretation. The book's very structure embodies this idea of co-creating meaning: each chapter begins with an encounter Meijer has had with the nonhumans who are the chapter's focus. In recounting these exchanges, they let the animals themselves participate in the making of meaning, too. Following the narrative openings, Meijer connects storytelling to philosophical reflection, drawing on diverse fields such as virtue ethics, eco-feminism, phenomenology, philosophy of language, and posthumanist political thought. This interplay

of lived encounter and theoretical analysis gives the book its distinctive texture, linking embodied experience with philosophical argument.

The reader first meets Olli, a Romanian street dog adopted by Meijer, with whom they shared many conversations, ranging from everyday aspects of cohabitation, such as food or walking routes, to more abstract themes such as joy, hope, and death. Touch played a particularly central role in their communication, helping them develop a shared language. Olli would, for instance, signal his presence during car rides by touching Meijer's shoulder with his nose, or seek their touch as reassurance that all was well. Meijer reads these experiences through a virtue-ethical lens, suggesting that qualities such as openness and kindness, as embodied by Olli, can and should inform everyday encounters between humans and non-human animals.

Unlike their interactions with Olli, Meijer's conversations with mice are guided less by touch than by voice (especially singing) and by material exchanges such as offering running wheels, cardboard, or hay. When observing how the mice respond, Meijer notes that their preferences are very individual and often differ significantly from one mouse to another. Yet what stands out most is the centrality of care within the mice community, taking the form of mutual grooming, supporting sick companions, and tending to the dead by washing and burying the bodies. Caring practices also shape Meijer's own relationship with the mice by feeding them and cleaning their house; and they regard the mice's companionship as a form of care in return. Such caring practices, Meijer suggests, resonate with eco-feminist scholarship in emphasizing our interconnectedness and rejecting atomistic understandings of human and nonhuman life.

A different kind of interspecies communication emerges in Meijer's encounters with their "amphibian neighbors," such as frogs, toads, and salamanders. Together with their human neighbors, Meijer helps these animals cross roads during seasonal migrations, protecting them from traffic. Through this collective practice, the group learns how to handle the animals

safely and deepens its understanding of their habits and movements. Meijer also finds their perception of nature transformed in the process, becoming more attuned to seasonal changes and more attentive to shared landscapes. They further observe a shift in the local community, which begins to see their environment differently, recognizing the road not as a mere human space but as a shared habitat with amphibians.

Moving beyond conversations with non-human animals, Meijer turns to the North Sea, asking what it can mean to speak with sea inhabitants and with the sea itself. By using the notion of “speaking” when describing interactions with the sea, Meijer offers another example of how they rethink the very idea of having a dialogue with someone or something. Even with an entity that is not a conscious interlocutor, like the sea, Meijer suggests that we can engage in forms of dialogue by being creative in how we interact. To illustrate this idea, they refer to initiatives such as the Embassy of the North Sea, which seeks to represent the North Sea politically, and the Sand Motor, an experiment where sand is deposited by humans and left for wind, waves, and animals to engage with, ultimately leading to the formation of dunes.

Drawing on these examples, Meijer suggests that conversations with the sea might begin by mapping existing human–sea interactions and by experimenting with material interventions that invite the sea to “speak.” In this context, they emphasize the importance of thinking about animals and plants together, using the philosophical lens of vegan eco-feminism. This line of thought points to the connections between the oppression of women and non-humans, including plants and animals, all of whom tend to be silenced in anthropocentric systems.

Meijer also explores other forms of conversation with nonhumans, including dialogues with art. Here, they examine what it means to be in conversation with one’s own artistic practice and how such exchanges can extend into public and political life. A very personal chapter looks inward as Meijer reflects on their experience of depression and considers how conversations with oneself can become a form of self-understanding. Meijer further explores

dialogues with children, who, similar to non-human animals, are strongly affected by the current ecological crises, yet remain excluded from the decisions that shape their futures. Building on their dialogues with children's groups, Meijer proposes incorporating children's perspectives through participatory assemblies that would enable them to take part in multispecies politics.

The book concludes with a shift in focus from speaking to listening, which Meijer sees as essential for cultivating meaningful multispecies conversations. As a first step toward establishing such listening practices, they propose identifying the different (deliberative) spheres in which political communication takes place. These can range from formal sites such as parliaments, media, and universities to spaces not usually seen as political, like homes, parks, or nature reserves. Across these settings, Meijer suggests, we can discover "entry points" for listening, i.e., spaces where we can become attentive to nonhuman voices.

These ideas are also enacted in the way the book is written and indeed, its composition is one of the book's central strengths. Framed as a dialogue with the reader, Meijer's writing embodies their philosophical commitments: By keeping the text open to multiple interpretations, they model the kind of dialogical engagement they invite us to practice when thinking about multispecies coexistence.

Furthermore, it is intriguing how Meijer weaves together personal narrative and philosophical reflection, moving seamlessly between experiential accounts of nonhuman encounters and their articulation within philosophical frameworks. As such, the book, while written accessibly for a general audience, also holds strong appeal for academic readers interested in animal ethics, political philosophy, and environmental thought.

Perhaps the book's greatest strength is how convincingly it shows, on the basis of personal experience, that communication with non-humans is not only possible but often already part

of our daily lives. Importantly, Meijer shows this not merely through familiar cases (such as dogs), where interspecies understanding may seem easier to grasp, but also through relationships with mice, frogs, art, or nature itself, where the possibility of communication might surprise readers. This contribution is crucial in a world that is marked by deep-seated skepticism and ignorance about the capacities of non-humans. Meijer's book thus offers a compelling counter-narrative to the assumption that non-humans are voiceless, showing instead that the limits of interspecies dialogue are largely set by our willingness to listen (even if, as I discuss later on, further significant constraints can arise from the risk of anthropomorphism, which Meijer seems to neglect).

While the book is primarily concerned with exploring the possibilities and practices of multispecies dialogue, it also seems designed to raise broader questions for the reader. One of these questions concerns the constraints of everyday life. Many of the practices Meijer describes for cultivating multispecies attunement require time, energy, and emotional availability. Such devotion is certainly not possible for everyone, particularly for those already stretched thin by the demands of daily life. From this perspective, the book might be read as inspirational, inviting us to think creatively about what forms of attention and care might be individually possible (and mutually beneficial) within the limits of ordinary life.

Another question concerns scalability. The scenes Meijer describes are often moving in their intimacy, yet they prompt the reader to wonder how interspecies care might be translated from this micro level to broader contexts. If multispecies dialogue is essential to creating a more just world for nonhumans, we must also ask how to account for the sheer number of nonhuman animals, let alone nonhuman nature more broadly. Clearly, we cannot speak to all of them. In what sense, then, does this limitation challenge the possibilities of multispecies participation? And especially when it comes to acknowledging individual differences among animals (as Meijer vividly shows in their interactions with the mice) what does it mean, from

an ethical perspective, that we cannot recognize those differences on a larger scale? Thus, while Meijer's examples beautifully capture what interspecies care can look like on a personal level, they also invite reflection on how such practices might be incorporated into socio-political life more broadly.

Finally, there is the question of interpretation. From the outset, Meijer rightly rejects what they call "species skepticism," i.e., the view that we cannot know or understand other animals. Yet in opposing this skepticism, they at times seem to risk the opposite bias: speaking with a degree of certainty about animals' inner lives that may exceed what we can know. For instance, they describe their dog Olli's greeting habits as expressions of "respect" and "politeness" and recount that he felt "honored" when his veterinarian came to visit him in his final hours. This is not to say that these interpretations are mistaken; given the deep friendship between Meijer and Olli, their readings of his expressions seem very plausible. But Meijer's confidence in these interpretations raises the broader question of how we can speak with nonhumans without falling into the trap of anthropomorphism, that is, the projection of human emotions, expressions, or motives onto nonhuman beings.

This risk seems even greater when interacting with animals we know less well than companion animals - yet engaging with less familiar species is just as essential if multispecies coexistence is to be genuinely inclusive. It therefore seems crucial to strike a balance that avoids both species skepticism and anthropomorphic projection. Such a balance can allow us to seize the possibilities of interspecies dialogue while remaining aware of the limits of human understanding. However, on this point Meijer's account is surprisingly silent: while the book offers ample examples of interspecies encounters, it does not address how we can achieve a balance between avoiding species skepticism and resisting anthropomorphic projection. It is, admittedly, a fine line to walk and certainly not always easy to avoid slipping

toward one side or the other. Yet this, I think, is precisely the challenge that we must embrace when speaking with nonhuman beings.

Ultimately, I wish to offer these reflections in the same spirit in which the book was written: as a contribution to the conversation that Meijer invites their readers to join, in a continuing effort to co-imagine our shared future in a more-than-human world.*

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